

CYSTINE AND METHIONINE IN THE PROTEIN FROM THE SEEDS OF CARILLA FRUIT

By J. W. AIRAN AND N. D. GHATGE

Two sulphur-containing essential amino-acids, cystine and methionine, have been estimated in carilla fruit seed-cakes.

After the successive extraction of the seeds of Carilla fruit (*Momordica Charantia*, N.O. Cucurbitaceae) with organic solvents like petroleum ether, benzene, chloroform and alcohol, the residue was found to contain nitrogen and sulphur. The albumin, isolated from this residue according to the method adopted by Basu, Nath, Ghani and Mukherjee (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1937, **24**, 4, 1027), was subjected to van Slyke's process (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1911-12, **10**, 15) as modified by Plummer and Rosedale (*Biochem. J.*, 1925, **19**, 1015) for the study of nitrogen distribution on the one hand, and Callan and Toennies method (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1941, **13**, 450) for cystine estimation, and to Horn, Jones and Blum's method (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1946, **166**, 313) for methionine estimation on the other. It contained 0.967% total sulphur, out of which 0.3647% was accounted for by cystine, and 0.3132% by methionine. The percentages of these essential amino-acids were 1.37 for cystine and 1.56 for methionine.

Since these seeds are not discarded in most of the preparations where the Carilla fruit is used as vegetable, these figures have a significance, and hence they are put along with the figures for some of the common seed meals below, the data being taken from Block and Bolling ("The Amino-acid Composition of Proteins and Foods", 1945, p. 195).

	%Cystine.	%Methionine.
Peanut meal	1.6	0.9
Cottonseed ..	2.0	1.6
Soyabean ..	1.3	1.3
Carilla seedcakes (present work)	0.0841	0.0957

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Total Sulphur.—It was estimated by means of Parr's sulphur bomb; 0.2045 g. of protein yielded 0.01429 g. of barium sulphate which corresponded to 0.967% sulphur.

Cystine.—Protein (1 g.) and potassium permanganate (10 g.) were added to NaOH solution (6.4 g. in 150 c.c. water). The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 48 hours, after which period the excess of the permanganate was destroyed with methyl alcohol. It was then acidified and the insoluble portion filtered off. The filtrate was boiled with bromine water, and then the sulphate ions were precipitated as barium sulphate, and treated in the usual manner. The precipitate weighed 0.0266 g. which corresponded to 0.3647% sulphur in the sample, and hence to 1.37% cystine.

Methionine.—The protein (0.5594 g.) was refluxed on a sand-bath with 15 c.c. of 20% hydrochloric acid for 18 hours. After this period, the hydrolysate was concentrated to nearly 5 c.c. and then treated with a small quantity of vegetable charcoal, and filtered. The filtrate was then made to 100 c.c. and 50 c.c. of this solution were withdrawn and concentrated to 10 c.c. roughly. It was then filtered and made exactly to 10 c.c. and 2 c.c. of this taken for estimation. Three small glass bottles were taken; one of these was taken for the "blank" experiment, one for the "unknown", and the third for the "standard". For this estimation, an authentic sample of methionine was obtained from the B.D.H.

Into each of these the following reagents were added in the order given below :

"Blank".	"Unknown".	"Standard".
2 c.c. soln.	2 c.c. soln.	2 c.c. soln.
3 c.c. distilled water	3 c.c. distilled water	3 c.c. dist. water
	1 c.c. sodium nitro- prusside soln., 10%	1 c.c. sodium nitro- prusside soln., 10%.
1 c.c. 5N-NaOH soln.	0.1 c.c. 5N-NaOH soln.	0.1 c.c. 5N-NaOH

After these additions were made, the three bottles were shaken for 10 minutes and then to each of these, 2 c.c. of 3% glycine solution were added and again shaken for 10 minutes, and finally 2 c.c. of phosphoric acid were added. The bottles were then shaken and kept aside for 5 minutes.

The bottle marked "blank" did not develop any colour. The solutions from the other two bottles were then taken for comparison of their colours. The readings with the Dubosq colorimeter were :

1.	22 "unknown"	9.4 "standard"
2.	32.2 "	13.4 "
3.	35.6 "	15.2 "

2 C.c. of the "standard" taken for comparison contained 0.002 g. of methionine, whence the amount of methionine in the sample taken for analysis was 0.5594 g. or 1.529% in the protein. This would account for 0.3741% of the total sulphur.

The albumin isolated was 6.135% of the seed-cake. Therefore the percentages of cystine and methionine in the seed-cakes work out to 0.0841 and 0.0957 respectively.